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Images from camera traps taken in 2020–2021 used to analyse biodiversity and monitor the saiga population in the Stepnoi Reserve, Astrakhan province, Russia

The principle of non-interference in wildlife is fundamental in the work of protected area staff, and currently available technologies allow for the study of biodiversity with minimal impact. Camera traps have proved themselves a useful non-invasive method of studying mammals, birds, and other wildlife. Monitoring with camera traps makes it possible to obtain large amounts of information, including species diversity, numbers, and population density, as well as to study various aspects of animal ecology. Another undeniable advantage of camera traps is the ability to record rare and nocturnal species that are difficult to survey in other ways.

In the Stepnoy Zakaznik, an almost year-round habitat for much of the North-western pre-Caspian saiga population, camera traps were installed quite recently. They have already become an integral part of the work of the reserve and a huge help in

monitoring and researching the animals' behaviour. Although it has been impossible to use camera traps to estimate the size of the saiga population because of difficulties with identification of individuals, the images obtained serve a source of information

about their seasonal and daily activity, especially in places frequented by the animals.

This report presents the results of the analysis of archival camera trap images from the Stepnoy Zakaznik taken in 2020–2021. The camera traps were installed near three small bodies of water formed by flooding artesian wells (Fig. 1).

The analysis involved 38,151 photographs taken by camera traps of three models – SEELock S308, SEELock S108 and Browning BTC-7A, which were placed at a height of about 1 m above the ground. The following data were entered in the table: animal type (if identifiable), time and date of the image, number of individuals of a photographed species and, wherever possible, sex and age. To avoid recording the same individual several times, each species was only recorded if there was an interval of at least two hours between observations.

A total of 33 species was recorded, including 24 species of birds and 9 mammals. The most recorded birds were ruddy shelduck *Tadorna ferruginea* (182 pictures), black-winged

Groups of male saigas (left) and a pack of wolves (right) near a field station at B3 location. Photo by Stepnoy Zakaznik

Fig. 1. Distribution of camera traps across the territory of the Stepnoy Zakaznik.
1 – lakes formed by artesian wells,
2 – locations of camera traps.

stilt *Himantopus himantopus* (52) and western marsh harrier *Circus aeruginosus* (51). The last two species frequenting only one of the three locations: *Himantopus himantopus* B2 and *Circus aeruginosus* B1. The long-legged buzzard *Buteo rufinus* was recorded three times at location B1. Important protected bird species such as steppe eagle *Aquila nipalensis* (17 pictures), demoiselle crane *Anthropoides virgo* (24) and cinereous vulture *Aegypius monachus* (15) were also regularly recorded. Among mammals, the most recorded species were saiga *Saiga tatarica* (827 pictures) and red fox *Vulpes vulpes* (479). The steppe wolf *Canis lupus campestris* (102 pictures). Secretive mammals such as corsac fox *Vulpes corsac* (28 pictures, 22 of which were at location B1) and Asian steppe wildcat *Felis lybica ornata* (4 pictures at location B1) also visited the watering holes quite regularly. In general, locations B1 and B3 yielded almost equal numbers of representatives of different species, with higher species diversity at B1.

In total, 10,842 saigas were recorded in the photos, with 6,901 pictures taken at location B3, 4,161 at B1, and 590 at B2. The average group size was approximately 13 saigas in both 2020 and 2021, while the average number of adult males in the groups increased from 3 individuals in 2020 to 5 in 2021. The largest total number of males was recorded at location B3 – 1,481 individuals, with 609 at location B1 and 141 at B2, which is roughly proportional to the total number of saiga photo records in each of the locations.

An analysis of seasonal and daily dynamics helped identify several patterns. In winter, the average number of saigas per photograph is noticeably smaller (on average 4 individuals, with the minimum of 2.5 individuals in December), while in spring and summer it is higher – about 16 individuals on average. In autumn, the average number of saigas in one image is 13 (Fig. 2). The largest number of saiga groups was registered in August and December 2020 (149 groups in each

case). The largest group (145 individuals) was recorded on 22nd September 2020 at location B3. Changes in the average numbers of saiga recorded throughout the day are reflected in Figure 2. Average group size decreases at night, which may be associated not so much with saiga behaviour as with the resolution of the cameras in night mode, which made it possible to count only individuals coming sufficiently close to the trap. Saiga numbers at watering holes increased from dawn to the middle of the day. According to the literature, in the periods of the highest average daily temperature, saigas prefer to rest (Sokolov, Zhirnov, 1998), and the photos show that watering holes are an important resting place for the animals. In the evening, saigas probably leave the watering holes to graze.

The saiga groups captured by the camera traps varied in sex and age composition, although sex and age are often hard to discern due to the low resolution of the cameras and overlapping images of different individuals.

Fig. 2. Seasonal and daily dynamics of the size of saiga groups in 2020–2021.

The graphs present combined data on observations for two years, by month and hour.

Left: Monthly group size. Bars – mean group size; Y-axis – months; Orange line – mean number of males.

Right: Mean group size by hour.

Mixed groups of both sexes with young, as well as groups of females with young were recorded from June to October (the earliest record of a young saiga was made on 1st May); separate groups of males were especially common in November and December, which is associated with the rutting period; however, starting from the end of November, the number of mixed groups of males and females begins to grow. The largest number of adult males recorded in a group was 47, with the average number of adult males in

mixed groups estimated at four individuals, which is approximately 30% of the average group size.

Although the images taken by camera traps do not provide reliable information about population size, they make it possible to indirectly assess changes, including in the number of adult males in a population, seasonal variations in sex and age composition associated with phases in the life cycle, daily activity and other extremely important ecological and ethological characteristics.

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